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LINGUISTIC COMPETENCE OF SENIOR HIGH SCHOOL STUDENTS IN ORMOC CITY

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ABSTRACT

This study is concerned with linguistic competence and relationship between the socio-demographic profile in terms of parents' education background and assigned household chores. The researcher made questionnaires and essay tests and administered among senior high school students who were randomly chosen as respondents. To analyze and interpret data, mean, standard deviation, T-test, and One-Way Analysis of Variance were utilized. ANOVA was conducted to determine whether there was a significant relationship between the socio-demographic profile and the level of linguistic competency of the senior high school students. Findings revealed that there was no significant relationship between the parents' educational attainment and linguistic competences. ANOVA was conducted again to determine whether there was a significant relationship between the assigned household chores and the level of linguistic competency of the senior high school students. Similarly, results indicate that linguistic competences do not differ among respondents with different assigned household chores. In addition, T-test was conducted to determine whether there was a significant difference among the level of linguistic competencies of the senior high school students in Ormoc City Regional Sports Academy, but the gathered results revealed that there was no significant difference among linguistic competence level. However, there was a significant difference in the linguistic competence in organization of ideas among senior high school students. Grade 11 students have significantly higher mean in organization of ideas than Grade 12 students. Major findings revealed that the respondents were at the basic level under the Common European Framework of References for Languages. Generally, the linguistic competence of the senior high school students should be improved. A proposed remedial activity in English writing skills is adapted to level up the linguistic competence of the senior high school students.

Keywords: *Linguistic Competence, Remedial Activity, Significant Relationship, Significant Differences, Basic, Independent, Proficient*

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INTRODUCTION

English as a second language in the Philippine setting plays a vital role in various aspects of life including academics, business world, and social media. Developing the linguistic competence of the student plays a crucial role in assessing them to succeed in their personal and academic life. Classroom instructions and activities are delivered in a blended learning modality (digital and printed module, online) due to pandemic. It is a hard time for the students to participate classroom activities specifically in answering the modules. They have limited interactions during online classes and cannot produce written outputs in the google classroom.

This study is focused on the linguistic competence in terms of development of ideas, organization of ideas, and language facility and conventions. This is one of the most important macro skills that involves careful study and investigation.

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The results of the study will provide necessary information that will contribute and enhance the linguistic competency level of the senior high school students. This will also be the bases for attaining effective communication which is a high demand skill needed in producing excellent outputs. In the workplace, the study is significant to various stakeholders. Teachers will be able to help the students convey the origins of words and languages, their historical applications, and their modern-day relevance. This approach helps students gain a better, more in-depth understanding of their assignments and work product expectations. Through this, the school administrators are responsible for preparing and providing teachers with essential competencies to allow them to perform successfully. It requires the teacher for further opportunities to study and attend seminars to possess many competencies and skills related to their field of work.

Research Questions

This study assesses the levels of linguistic competency among the Senior High School Students in Ormoc City regional Sports Academy. Specifically, the study aims to answer the following questions:

1. What is the socio-demographic profile of the learners in terms of:
 - 1.1. Parent's Education Background?
 - 1.2. Assigned Household Chores?
2. What is the level of linguistic competency of the respondents in terms of the following:
 - 2.1. Development of Ideas?
 - 2.2. Organization of Ideas?
 - 2.3. Language Facility and Conventions?
3. Is there a significant relationship between the socio-demographic profile and the level of linguistic competency of the Senior High School students?
4. Is there a significant difference among the level of linguistic competencies of the senior high school students in Ormoc City Regional Sports Academy?
5. What appropriate remedial activities should be proposed to improve the levels of linguistic competence of senior high school students?

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Research Design

Quantitative research design is used in this study. The researcher has clearly defined questions to which objective answers were sought. All aspects of the study were carefully designed before data is given. And to investigate the level of linguistic competence of the two different grade levels of students in Ormoc City Regional Sports Academy, the researcher used tools, such as questionnaires or computer software, to collect numerical data. This quantified the problem by way of generating numerical data or data that can be transformed into usable statistics.

Research Respondents

The study was conducted among the Senior High School students in Ormoc City Regional Sports Academy, Ormoc City, Leyte, the only senior high school offering a sports track in the whole region V111. It is situated in the heart of the city at Carlos Tan Street and had started its operation in the school

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year 2016-2017, with a school head and four teachers who vested ample time and efforts in catering and nurturing 53 males and 28 female- students who were both in the grade 11. In the following school year of 2017-2018, only 37 grade 11 students were enrolled and only 57 out of 81 students were successfully completed their senior high school studies due to several factors such as economic crises and family problems that arose along the way. In its 5th year of operation, pandemic struck and affected the whole educational system, and the new mode of learning came to an open. The school is still catering for two hundred (200) students from all walks of life, coming from 66 different places in Leyte. And since the system is new, teachers adapted the blended learning approach fitted to the needs of the students. During submission and retrievals of their outputs, the researcher found out that students differ in their linguistic competencies.

Research Instrument

The survey questionnaire is personally designed together with the narratives and essay tests. These narratives and essay tests were modified by the researcher in accordance with the content areas and competencies from the subjects Reading and Writing and English for Academic and Professional Purposes. These tests were validated by two master teachers in English from other senior high schools in Ormoc City Division.

Part I of the instrument is on the socio-demographic profile of the respondent in terms of parent's educational background and assigned household chores. The respondents checked the data confirming the educational attainment of their parents (both mother and father), including the chores assigned to them daily or in weekly bases.

Part II is on the level of linguistic competence of senior high school students in terms of development of ideas, organization of ideas, and language facility and conventions. Different levels of linguistic competence of the respondents have rating scales: 91-95 for proficient level, 86-90 for independent level, and 80-85 in the basic level. The different scales were adapted from the Common European Framework of Reference for Languages (2018). The Common European Framework for Reference and Languages has been used because it provides a standardized way to measure a learner's progress and allowing teachers to avoid inconsistencies in the measurement of students' levels. To identify the levels of linguistic competence among senior high school students in Ormoc City Regional Sports Academy, written outputs in the Learning Answer Sheets based were utilized. There were four written outputs selected in this study. For grade 11 students, they were asked to make narratives about "Memoir" and "Distance Learning". Similarly, "Descriptive Essay Test" and a "Reaction Paper" were made by grade 12 students. Scoring is dependent on the linguistic competence: development of ideas =15 points; organization of ideas =25 points; and language facility and conventions =10 points. The scores of each LAS are added to sum up a total of 100 points per student in a grade level.

Data Analysis

After the finalization of the designed instrument and the approval of the study by the panel, the researcher sought the permission and endorsement from the Schools Division Superintendent of Ormoc City Division. The researcher also sent a formal letter to the English Program Supervisor, and the School Head of Ormoc City Regional Sports Academy where the study is conducted. The questionnaires were distributed personally to the respondents and facilitate data gathering and retrieval. The respondents were given a maximum of two-week duration to submit the required data, including the essays and narratives.

The socio-demographic profile in terms to the respondent's parental level of education and the assigned household chores were used. This was analyzed by using descriptive statistics through frequency counting and percentages by using the formula: $P=f/N \times 100$

The second objective was focused on identifying the level of linguistic competence of the respondents in terms of development of ideas, organization of ideas, and language facility and conventions in their academic writing from the retrieved LAS. Data on Learning Activity Sheets were manually encoded with the use of Grammarly checker to identify the linguistic competence of the respondents. Grammar checker automatically gave results and identified the errors with names and colors in each competency being tested. The scores were then counted and added to determine the level of linguistic competency among the respondents. The ratings from narratives and essays were added in terms of development of ideas, organization of ideas, and language facility and conventions. Then the scores were identified as to basic (80-85), independent (86-90), and proficient (91-95) levels. The Common European Framework of Reference for Languages was used in identifying the levels of linguistic competence. In the basic level, learners were able to respond to tasks and accomplished their communicative purposes to be developed effectively. Texts include appropriately varied simple, compound, and complex sentence types. Words and phrases are suitable for the topics, purposes, and audiences. Substantial knowledge of spelling, grammar usage, capitalization, and punctuation are evident.

Likewise, in the independent level, learners should address the tasks effectively and fully accomplish their communicative purposes. Texts are coherent and well-structured with respect to these purposes and include well-crafted and effective connections and transitions. Their ideas are developed in a logical, clear, and effective manner. Moreover, in proficient level, learners were able to address the tasks strategically, fully accomplish their communicative purposes, demonstrate a skillful and creative approach in constructing and delivering messages. All ideas in the texts are developed clearly, logically, effectively and in focus. Supporting details and examples strengthened both effectiveness and rhetorical power of the texts.

The significant relationship between the socio-demographic profile and the level of linguistic competence of the senior high school students of Ormoc City Regional Sports Academy was determined using one-way analysis of variance (one-way ANOVA).

Similarly, the significant difference among the level of linguistic competencies of the senior high school students in Ormoc City Regional Sports Academy was identified again by one-way analysis of variance (one-way ANOVA).

After gathering and analyzing data, the researcher proposed a remedial activity in English writing skills. Its primary purpose is not simply enhancing the linguistic competencies of students, but also guiding ways that enable them to understand and use language in real life situations.

RESEARCH FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

This chapter contains a detailed presentation and discussion of data analysis and the results of this study. The findings are presented under the following major headings: Socio-demographic profile consisting of parent's educational level and regular daily/weekly chores; and level of linguistic competence which are based on the Common European Framework of Reference (CEFR) for Languages.

Socio-demographic profile of respondents

One of the contributing factors that affect the linguistic competency level of the senior high school students is the socio-demographic profile. The term "socio-demographic" is a combination of social status and demographics. Social status is the level of value a person is considered to possess. Similarly,

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demographics are the statistical characteristics of human populations such as parent's educational background and doing assigned household chores.

Parents' Education Background

Educational attainment of parents refers to the highest level of education that he/she has successfully completed. The data shows that out of the six educational attainments of the respondent's parents, 62% fathers and 58% attained secondary education. Only 2 out of 100 mothers have attained complete college education with MA units and none for fathers. The result implies that the students are coming from different barangays in the different towns of Leyte. Most of their parents were not able to attain higher education because of early marriage. Another reason is that many were prone to earn a living at an early age especially that most of them were 23 staying in an agricultural area where planting rice, vegetables, and sugarcane is a way of living.

Table 1. Distribution on the socio-demographic profile of respondents.

Indicators	Frequency	Percentage (%)
N=100		
A. Parent's Educational Level		
Father		
Primary	16	16
Secondary	62	62
Technical/Vocational	10	10
Degree/Undergraduate	12	12
Master/Ph.D.	0	0
Mother		
Primary	20	20
Secondary	58	58
Technical/Vocational	10	10
Degree/Undergraduate	10	10
Master/Ph.D.	2	02
B. Regular Daily/Weekly Chores		
Cleaning the house	28	28
Watching Siblings	26	26
Preparing meals	22	22
Doing the laundry	12	12
Operating family business	8	08
Others: Farming	4	04

Assigned Household Regular daily/weekly chores. The results show that the highest percentage:28% of the respondents were assigned in cleaning the house, 26% in watching siblings, 22% were tasked in preparing meals, and 4% involved in farming. Students were obliged to do these assigned household chores just to help their parents who are earnestly earning a living to augment the necessities of family. Despite hardships in their new mode of learning: blended online and modular studies brought about by the COVID-19 pandemic, students were able to divide their time in learning and doing the household chores. Among the respondents, there were only 4 who engaged in farming

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for there are few rural areas in the locality wherein farming is a source of living. These students tend to help their parents in the farm while doing their tasks in studying and answering modules.

Levels of Linguistic Competence. Linguistic competence as one focus of this study was being tested among 100 respondents from the senior high school in Ormoc City Regional Sports Academy. Three competences were given to identify and determine the level of linguistic competence among senior high school students. The researcher designed instruments such as narrative writings for the grade 11 and essay writings for grade 12. Development of ideas is one of the competences tested. Students here write narratives and essays with thesis statement supported by the main idea, supporting details, and concrete examples. It is given a perfect score of 15 points.

Next observed is how the ideas were organized. Coherent and cohesion of the relevant ideas is being tested and scored 25 points.

Language facility and conventions is the last competency tested. Knowledge on basic grammar like spelling, punctuation, and capitalization were considered and given a score of 10 points.

Common European Framework of Reference for Languages scaling is used. The linguistic competences of the students were measured and categorized as to basic level (80-85), independent level (86-90), and proficient level (91-95). The overall outputs of the respondents were in the basic level in terms of development of ideas which is 83.5, its organization of ideas is 81.5, and 84.5 for language facility and conventions. Based on the result, it was found out that the respondents have the lowest levels in linguistic competence in the development of ideas, organization of ideas, and language facility and conventions both in narrative and essay writing tests. The result is reflected in Table 3.2

Table 2. Levels of Linguistic Competence of the Senior High School Students

Linguistic Competence	Average Scale			Level of Linguistic Competence	Interpretation
	Narrative Writing	Essay Tests	Average		
Development of ideas	82	85	83.5	Basic	Main idea, supporting details, and examples do not support the thesis statement.
Organization of ideas	81	82	81.5	Basic	Lacks organization, coherence, and cohesion of relevant ideas.
Language Facility and Convention	84	85	84.5	Basic	Knows very little of basic grammar and has considerable errors.
Overall	82	84	83	Basic	
Legend:					
81-85	Basic				
86-90	Independent				

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Relationship between the socio-demographic profile of father's educational attainment and the level of linguistic competency.

The researcher gathered the data and analyzed the results using one-way analysis of variance (one-way ANOVA) to find the significant relationship between the socio-demographic profile and the level of linguistic competency of the senior high school students.

After analysis of the data the researcher finds no significant relationship between parents' educational attainment and the linguistic competence of senior high school students in terms of development of ideas, organization of ideas, and language facility and conventions. It differs to the findings stated by Kalil et. al (2012), RMA Khan, (2015), KL Jensen (2017), and G. Kalaya (2018), and other researchers that there is a positive significant relationship or great impact of parental education status at students' level of linguistic competence and or academic success.

Table 3.1. ANOVA table on the Relationship between the Father's Educational Attainment and the level of linguistic competency

Source of Variation		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean of Squares	F	p-value	Significance
Development of Ideas	Between Groups	11.434	4	2.859	.889	.478	Not Significance
	Within Groups	144.746	45	3.217			
	Total	156.180	49				
Organization of Ideas	Between Groups	38.329	4	9.582	1.861	.134	Not Significance
	Within Groups	231.671	45	5.148			
	Total	270.000	49				
Language Facility and Conventions	Between Groups	4.219	4	1.055	.795	.535	Not Significance
	Within Groups	59.701	45	1.327			
	Total	63.920	49				

***Significant at 5% level**

Table 3.1. is summarizing the ANOVA analysis of the relationship between the Father's Educational attainment and the level of linguistic competence of the Senior High school students. The p-value of all the linguistic competencies is greater than the 0.050 significance level. It shows the results on the relationship between the Father's Educational Attainment and the level of linguistic competencies. ANOVA was conducted to determine whether there was a significant relationship between the socio-demographic profile and the level of linguistic competency of the Senior High School students. According to the obtained findings, there was no significant relationship between the father's different educational attainment and Linguistic Competencies; (1) The level of linguistic competencies: Development of ideas, Organization of ideas, and Language Facility and Conventions of the senior high school students do not differ with respect to fathers' educational attainment. Further, it implies that there might be other factors to be considered aside from the educational background of father. Some of these factors might be their learning behavior and learning habits, school quality, and desires.

Relationship between the socio-demographic profile of the mother's educational attainment and the level of linguistic competency.

Table 3.2. ANOVA table on the Relationship between Mother's Educational Attainment and the Level of Linguistic Competency

Source of Variation		Sum of Squares	df	Mean of Squares	F	p-value	Significance
Development of Ideas	Between Groups	6.812	4	1.703	.513	.726	Not Significance
	Within Groups	149.368	45	3.319			
	Total	156.180	49				
Organization of Ideas	Between Groups	29.545	4	7.386	1.382	.255	Not Significance
	Within Groups	240.455	45	5.343			
	Total	270.000	49				
Language Facility and Conventions	Between Groups	5.656	4	1.295			Not Significance
	Within Groups	58.264	45				
	Total	63.920	49				

Table 3.2 shows the results on the relationship between the mother's educational attainment and the level of linguistic competencies. ANOVA was conducted to determine whether there was a significant relationship between the socio-demographic profile and the level of linguistic competency of the senior high school students. Based on the gained results, there was no significant relationship between the mother's different educational attainment and linguistic competencies. This means that the mother's educational attainment of the senior high school students has no effect on the level of linguistic competencies (Development of Ideas, Organization of Ideas and Language Facility and Conventions). Its implication might be the same with that of the father. The students may lack interest in their studies because of the new mode of learning, indifferent learning behaviors and styles, or may lack the desire to practice reading and writing. Therefore, this study does not conform to other studies that parents' educational background has a significant relationship to the linguistic competence of their children.

Table 3.3. ANOVA table on the relationship between the assigned household chores and the level of linguistic competency.

Linguistic Competence	Source of Variation	Sum of Squares	df	Mean of Squares	F	p-value	Significance
Development of Ideas	Between Groups	7.808	5	1.562	.463	.802	Not Significance
	Within Groups	148.372	44	3.372			
	Total	156.180	49				
Organization of Ideas	Between Groups	6.580	5	1.316	.220	.952	Not Significance
	Within Groups	263.420	44	5.987			
	Total	270.000	49				
Language Facility and Conventions	Between Groups	6.326	5	1.265	.967	.449	Not Significance
	Within Groups	57.594	44	1.309			
	Total	63.920	49				

Table 3.3 shows the results on the relationship between the Assigned Household Chores and the level of linguistic competencies. ANOVA was conducted to determine whether there was a significant

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relationship between the assigned household chores and the level of linguistic competency of the Senior High School students. According to the found results, there was no significant relationship between the assigned household chores and the level of linguistic competencies. This indicates that level of linguistic competences does not differ among respondents with different assigned household chores. The result of this study which is reflected in Table 3.3 contradicts the study of Pestana et al., (2016). According to his study, adolescents who collaborate with family members performing household chores have better school performance than those who do not. Best results might be dependent on the positive attitude of the learner. Self-motivation and parental participation may be another contributing factor to be studied. Therefore, this study revealed that household chores have no significant relationship with the level of linguistic competence of the senior high school students.

The next question in which this study aims to answer is about the significant difference among the level of linguistic competencies of the senior high school students in Ormoc City Regional Sports Academy. This was analyzed by using one-way analysis of variance (one-way ANOVA).

Difference between the Level of Linguistic Competency among Senior High School Students

Table 4. Differences in the level of linguistic competency among senior high school students.

Linguistic Competence	Grade Level	N	Mean	t-computed	df	p-value (2-tailed)	Significance
Development of Ideas	Grade 11	32	24.38	-1.085	48	.284	Not Significant
	Grade 12	18	24.94				
Organization of Ideas	Grade 11	32	41.50	4.755	47.526	.000	Significant
	Grade 12	18	39.00				
Language Faculty and conventions	Grade 11	32	17.78	-1.822	45.703	.075	Not Significant
	Grade 12	18	18.28				

Table 4 shows the differences in the level of linguistic competency among the senior high school students in Ormoc City Regional Sports Academy. T- test (Two tailed) was conducted to determine whether there was a significant difference among the level of linguistic competencies of the Senior High School students in Ormoc City Regional Sports Academy. According to the gathered results, there was no significant difference among the level of linguistic competencies. However, there was a significant difference in the linguistic competence in Organization of Ideas ($t = 4.755 < t_{0.05(48)} = 2.0106$; $p - value = 0.000 < 0.05$) among the Senior High School students in Ormoc City Regional Sports Academy. Grade 11 students has significantly higher mean ($\mu = 41.50$) in Organization of Ideas competency than Grade 12 which is ($\mu = 39.00$). It was found out that this group of students differs in goals, attitudes, and dreams in life. These respondents are more diligent in fulfilling their tasks on time, more studious, and preferred more on research, have an innate difference in intelligence, and variations in past learning experiences. Besides, written activities given were based on the unforgettable experiences they have in life: (1) Memoir, and (2) Distance Learning. Whereas grade 12 respondents were given higher level of tasks such as: Reaction Paper and Descriptive Essay which are not comparable, thus; differ in the organization of ideas. Altogether, the linguistic competences which are in the basic level, motivates the researcher to propose Remedial Activities aimed at helping the students' enhancement of the linguistic competency level. These activities are variety of intervention tactics on how to assess these needs of enhancing the linguistic competence and evaluating outcomes.

CONCLUSION

It was evident that the socio- demographic profile of the respondents in terms of parents' educational background and the assigned household chores have no significant relationship between the linguistic competence of the senior high school students in Ormoc City Regional Sports Academy. It can be concluded that parents' educational background and assigned specific household chores are not determinant factors affecting their linguistic competence.

The findings are limited only to the linguistic competence in writing skills in terms of development of ideas, organization of ideas, and language facility and conventions. The levels of linguistic competence of the respondents were interpreted as "Basic" which means 82.0 and 84.0, respectively. Therefore, both grades 11 and 12 students have the lowest levels of skills in writing that needs immediate remediation.

Furthermore, the results revealed that there is significant difference among the level of linguistic competencies of the senior high school students in Ormoc City Regional Sports Academy. Table 4 shows this difference. Grade 11 students has significantly higher mean (41.50) in organization of ideas competency than Grade 12 (39.00) students. This can be concluded that grade 11 students differed in goals, attitudes, and dreams in life compared to grade 12 students. Besides, the written activities were of different levels of comparison.

Finally, based on the major findings, a proposed module is designed to enhance the English writing skills of the senior high school students.

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